

Slot-loaded Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna for a Microwave Imaging System to Monitor Liver Microwave Thermal Ablation

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Abstract—This study presents the design and the experimental validation of a slot-loaded antipodal Vivaldi antenna for a microwave imaging system to monitor liver microwave thermal ablation. The antenna's overall dimension is equal to 40mm×65mm, and its working bandwidth goes from 600 MHz up to 3 GHz, with the possibility to operate at a higher frequency. The antenna is designed to operate inside a coupling medium that allows to scale down the antenna dimensions, as well as to improve the coupling of the electromagnetic power to the tissue. The antenna's S-parameters well agree with the simulation result. Finally, the antenna proposed in this work shows the most compact aperture dimension, as compared with other similar antennas designed for biomedical applications, working within the same bandwidth.

Index Terms—Vivaldi antenna, coupling medium, microwave imaging system, microwave thermal ablation

I. INTRODUCTION

Liver cancer is among the most common fatal malignancies, accounting for 9.1% of all cancer death globally [1]. Microwave thermal ablation (MTA) is considered an effective way to treat liver malignancy with a minimum invasive approach [2]. The procedure consists of placing a microwave antenna within the tumor to be treated; then, the antenna is fed with microwave power values up to 100 W for a duration of a few minutes (up to 10 min). In the clinical settings, MTA is flanked by conventional imaging modalities, such as fluoroscopy, ultrasound (US), computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), with different imaging purposes: treatment planning, targeting, monitoring, assessment treatment response, and follow-up [3]. However, real-time monitoring of the thermal ablation treatment remains an unsolved issue because all the existing modalities show different flaws when it comes to clinical procedures [3].

Therefore, the real-time assessment of thermal ablation treatments still heavily relies on the clinician's experience [4].

To improve the accuracy of thermal ablation treatments, microwave imaging (MWI) has been proposed as a novel approach for real-time treatment monitoring [5][6]. As compared to conventional modalities, microwave imaging has a number of attractive features such as portability, non-invasiveness, cost-effectiveness, and non-ionizing nature of the electromagnetic field [7].

Microwave imaging reconstructs the dielectric properties of the target by processing the electromagnetic (EM) field scattered by the investigated tissue. To this end, an antenna array is located above the body and used to probe the region of interest [7]. Accordingly, the adopted antennas play a crucial role in the performance of the system.

In [8], the numerical assessment of a microwave imaging system for real-time monitoring of a MTA procedure was demonstrated. The system consisted of 8 Vivaldi antennas placed in an array configuration placed in front of a 3D printed phantom mimicking the ablation zone. The achieved results show it is not only capable of localizing the target but also can identify the ablation zone at different ablation stages. In this paper, a novel slot-loaded Vivaldi antenna for the MWI system is designed and experimentally assessed. The proposed antenna is designed to work in the coupling medium as the antenna in [8]. Moreover, it has a more compact dimension. The antenna's performance was characterized in an array configuration. The result demonstrates that the slot-loaded Vivaldi antenna has good resistance towards the mutual coupling.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Antenna Design and Realization

In [9], the working conditions of a microwave imaging system to monitor thermal ablation of the liver were defined. In particular, a 0.5-2 GHz frequency band was settled. These conditions give a trade-off between penetration depth, imaging resolution, and antenna dimension. In this work, a new design for the antenna of the MWI system is proposed.

Figure 5 (a) antenna in the array configuration, and (b) measurement inside the coupling medium (Microwave Laboratory at University of Calabria).

Figure 6 Simulation and measurement result of two antennas in an array configuration

water from separating. The mixture consists of 37.8% of distilled water, 57.84% of sunflower oil, 0.42% of guar gum, and 3.94% of dishwashing detergent by weight.

The comparison between simulations and measurement results of one antenna in the coupling medium is reported in Figure 3, where a quite good agreement can be observed. From the S-parameter measured in the coupling medium, a matching from 600 MHz to 3 GHz is obtained, with the possibility of working even at higher frequencies. The E-field distribution of the antenna placed inside the coupling medium is shown in Figure 4. It can be seen that the E-field amplitude decreases as frequency increases. This is due to the fact that the coupling medium is lossier at higher frequencies.

In order to verify the antenna's performance in the array configuration, the antenna's matching is characterized when placing two antennas close to each other (see Figure 5(a)). The distance between each antenna is equal to 23mm, which is larger than a quarter wavelength at 1 GHz in the coupling medium. The experimental setup is demonstrated in Figure 5(b). The simulated and measurement result in Figure 6 shows that the antenna matching at a lower frequency, especially around 600 MHz, is maintained even in the presence of another antenna. This slot-loaded Vivaldi

antenna shows a very good resistance towards mutual coupling.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the design, realization and the experimental assessment of a slot-loaded antipodal Vivaldi antenna, to be adopted for a microwave imaging system for liver thermal ablation monitoring. The antenna is designed and characterized in the presence of a coupling medium specifically conceived for the system. The measured S-parameter of the single antenna well agrees with the simulation results, showing a matching from 600 MHz up to 3 GHz, with the possibility to work towards a higher frequency. The antenna matching in the array configuration proves the effectiveness of the slot-loaded design, by revealing also a good resistance toward the mutual coupling. The good matching is maintained even with the presence of another antenna. All the above features reveal that the antenna is suitable to be arranged into the array configuration needed by a microwave imaging device for monitoring liver ablation.

Future work will include the experimental assessment of two or more antenna elements in the array configuration, placed in the coupling medium with the presence of the liver phantom, and the measurement of the differential signal with the phantom.

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